

An Algebraic Representation of Notes and Intervals for Algorithmic Composition

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Abstract

In algorithmic music systems, especially those involving counterpoint and harmonic reasoning, it is essential to distinguish between enharmonically equivalent notes and isometric intervals. At the same time, efficient computation requires simple algebraic operations and access to musically meaningful equivalence classes.

This paper introduces a unified algebraic representation of notes and intervals based on a cyclic integer domain. The proposed model preserves enharmonic distinctions while reducing all operations to integer addition and subtraction. The construction is derived from a fundamental assumption relating chromatic alteration and octave equivalence.

1 Introduction

Standard computational representations, such as MIDI pitch numbers, usually collapse enharmonic distinctions:

$$C^\sharp = D^\flat.$$

However, in tonal music:

$$C^\sharp \neq D^\flat.$$

Similarly, intervals spanning the same number of semitones may have different musical meanings:

augmented second \neq minor third.

A representation suitable for algorithmic composition must therefore preserve enharmonic spelling, interval structure, and computational simplicity. This is particularly important in systems involving counterpoint or harmony, where the functional role of a note or interval cannot be reduced to its sounding pitch alone.

The main contribution of this work is a minimal algebraic representation in which:

- notes and intervals are encoded in a single cyclic domain,
- enharmonic spelling is preserved,
- diatonic and chromatic equivalence classes are obtained through simple projections,
- all basic operations reduce to integer addition and subtraction.

The system was originally developed as the basic musical representation layer for an algorithmic composition program devoted to assisted fugue writing.

2 Equivalence Classes

Two projections are required.

2.1 Diatonic Projection

For notes, the diatonic projection identifies the note name independently of alteration:

$$D^\sharp, D^{\sharp\sharp}, D, D^\flat \mapsto D.$$

For intervals, the analogous projection identifies the interval degree independently of quality:

$$\text{minor third, major third, augmented third} \mapsto \text{third}.$$

2.2 Pitch-Class Projection

A second projection identifies the chromatic pitch class, optionally with octave information. This is the representation needed to convert the result of symbolic algorithms into playable or notatable forms, such as MIDI output or score notation.

3 Fundamental Assumption

We assume that a note altered by twelve successive chromatic semitones is equivalent to the original note in both the diatonic and pitch-class equivalence relations, and corresponds exactly to the same note one octave higher:

$$C_n^{\sharp^{12}} = C_{n+1}.$$

Thus, accidentals are periodic modulo 12, and twelve chromatic alterations correspond to one octave.

4 Algebraic Construction

Let:

- 0 represent the reference note C_0 ,
- 1 represent an ascending perfect fifth.

Since successive perfect fifths generate all pitch spellings, including altered notes, every note or interval can first be represented by an integer:

$$n \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

We define the musical algebraic domain

$$\mathcal{N} = \mathbb{Z}_{4032},$$

referred to here as the *fifth-generated cyclic domain*.

4.1 Projections

From a value $n \in \mathcal{N}$, the diatonic function is obtained by:

$$d(n) = n \bmod 7.$$

The pitch class is obtained by:

$$p(n) = n \bmod 12.$$

The projection $p(n) = n \bmod 12$ yields the pitch class, but not in the conventional chromatic order. Instead, the resulting values follow the order induced by successive perfect fifths:

$$0, 7, 2, 9, 4, 11, 6, 1, 8, 3, 10, 5,$$

which corresponds to the ordering induced by the cycle of fifths.

To recover the standard chromatic ordering

$$0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11,$$

one can apply a simple linear transformation:

$$c = 7p \bmod 12.$$

Since $7^{-1} \equiv 7 \pmod{12}$, this transformation is self-inverse, and the same operation converts between the fifth-based ordering and the conventional chromatic ordering in both directions.

The octave is obtained by:

$$o(n) = \left\lfloor \frac{7n}{12} \right\rfloor \bmod 48.$$

Figure 1 summarizes the three fundamental projections obtained from the same algebraic value.

Notes and intervals share the same cyclic domain,
but notes are points and intervals are displacements.

Figure 1: The algebraic representation maps a single cyclic value to the main musical equivalence classes: diatonic function, pitch class, and octave.

5 Periodicity

Twelve chromatic alterations correspond to 84 perfect fifths:

$$12 \Rightarrow 84.$$

Each fifth spans seven semitones. Therefore:

$$84 \cdot \frac{7}{12} = 49.$$

Thus, 84 fifths correspond to 49 octaves in chromatic terms. However, by the fundamental assumption, they must correspond to exactly one octave. Therefore:

$$49 \equiv 1 \Rightarrow 48 \equiv 0.$$

This induces a periodicity of 48 octaves. The complete period is therefore:

$$4032 = 48 \cdot 84.$$

The value 4032 is the smallest period ensuring consistency between fifth-based generation and octave equivalence under the imposed accidental periodicity.

Within this domain, the value 84 represents an octave shift.

6 Notes and Intervals

Notes and intervals share the same underlying cyclic domain, but they have different semantic roles. A note is a point in musical space, whereas an interval

is a displacement between points. Thus, notes form an affine space over the additive group of intervals.

The meaningful operations are:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Note} - \text{Note} &= \text{Interval}, \\ \text{Note} + \text{Interval} &= \text{Note}, \\ \text{Note} - \text{Interval} &= \text{Note}, \\ \text{Interval} + \text{Interval} &= \text{Interval}, \\ \text{Interval} - \text{Interval} &= \text{Interval}. \end{aligned}$$

The operation $\text{Note} + \text{Note}$ is intentionally undefined.

Although a note can be regarded as an interval from a chosen origin such as C_0 , maintaining the distinction between points and displacements makes the algebraic structure more precise and prevents musically meaningless operations.

7 Examples

7.1 Fifths and Octaves

Starting from $C_0 = 0$:

$$G_0 = 1, \quad D_1 = 2, \quad A_1 = 3.$$

The note F_0 is represented by 83, since it is one descending fifth from C_0 , folded into the cyclic domain:

$$F_0 = -1 \equiv 83 \pmod{84}.$$

The octave extraction formula gives:

$$o(83) = \left\lfloor \frac{7 \cdot 83}{12} \right\rfloor \bmod 48 = 48 \bmod 48 = 0.$$

7.2 Enharmonic Distinction

In this representation:

$$C^\sharp = 7, \quad D^b = -5.$$

They share the same pitch class:

$$7 \bmod 12 = -5 \bmod 12,$$

but not the same diatonic function:

$$7 \bmod 7 \neq -5 \bmod 7.$$

Thus:

$$C^\sharp \neq D^b.$$

7.3 Interval Computation

Let:

$$B_3 = 89, \quad D_3 = 170.$$

Then:

$$I = B_3 - D_3 = -81.$$

This corresponds to a descending major sixth, or equivalently an ascending minor third under inversion, depending on the chosen interval orientation. The algebra preserves the signed direction of the interval.

7.4 Harmonic Operations

Let:

$$G_3 = 253.$$

Adding a perfect fourth gives:

$$G_3 + \text{perfect fourth} = 253 + 83 = 336 = C_4.$$

This corresponds to the expected tonal motion $G \rightarrow C$.

Adding an augmented fourth gives:

$$G_3 + \text{augmented fourth} = 253 - 246 = 7 = C_4^\sharp.$$

Adding a diminished fifth gives:

$$G_3 + \text{diminished fifth} = 253 + 330 = 583 = D_4^\flat.$$

The last two examples have the same pitch-class distance but preserve different interval spellings and therefore different functional identities.

8 Properties

The system has the following properties:

- closure under the meaningful addition and subtraction operations,
- preservation of enharmonic distinctions,
- preservation of interval degree and quality,
- direct access to diatonic and chromatic equivalence classes,
- computational simplicity through integer arithmetic.

9 Applications

The representation is particularly suitable for:

- algorithmic counterpoint,
- harmonic analysis,
- rule-based composition,
- real-time symbolic music systems.

In contrapuntal algorithms, for example, the ability to distinguish an augmented second from a minor third is essential even when both correspond to the same number of semitones. Likewise, the ability to convert the same symbolic result to pitch class or octave-bearing pitch makes the representation usable for playback and notation.

10 Related Work

Standard computational representations of musical pitch typically rely on MIDI note numbers or pitch-class encodings, which collapse enharmonic distinctions and therefore do not preserve functional differences between notes [1].

In music theory, the distinction between enharmonic spellings and interval qualities has long been recognized as structurally significant [2].

In computational musicology, several approaches address symbolic representations of pitch and interval structures, often focusing on pitch-class sets or frequency-based models [3].

Algebraic approaches to music theory have explored structures such as pitch-class spaces, the circle of fifths, and the Tonnetz [4]. These models describe relationships between musical objects, but typically assume a prior representation of pitch and interval structures.

Recent work has also explored algebraic representations of musical structures using strongly typed programming paradigms [5]. These approaches emphasize the distinction between notes and intervals and model musical transformations in a compositional way.

The approach proposed in this paper differs in that it defines a unified algebraic representation in which notes and intervals are elements of the same cyclic domain while preserving both diatonic and chromatic equivalence classes. To the best of the author’s knowledge, this specific construction does not appear in existing literature.

11 Conclusion

We presented a compact algebraic system for representing notes and intervals, preserving musical structure while enabling efficient computation. The model

provides a single cyclic domain from which diatonic function, pitch class, and octave can be extracted through simple operations.

Future work includes extensions to microtonal systems and alternative tuning frameworks.

References

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